

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)
Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication
ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060
Publisher: Binas Publishing
Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“NEVER FADE”

Whatever clothes you'll wear
You're still my Angel
And all of the times we've shared
Fears are taken as well

So, don't be scared
You know that I will be there
I always care for you MyLove
So, don't be afraid
You know this time was made
The two of us will never fade

Whatever dreams you have in mind
For me they are all fine
It only takes a matter of time
Have your patience be stretch a mile

So, worry a bit less
This struggle and this mess
It's temporary, I promise
So, hold your head up high
Thank God for our life
We'll always be by your side, Gryffyn and I